

**ENHANCING EFFECTIVENESS IN TEACHER EDUCATION
 PROGRAMMES THROUGH PERFORMANCE MANAGEMENT AND
 INTEGRATION OF LIFE SKILLS**

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If education has to prepare students for life and facilitate a successful and efficient transition from student's life to a professional well developed civilized one, then the educational goals need to be fixed for equipping them to live in world where, the key to success is the ability to be flexible, ability to change. They should possess tools and skills with the capability to apply them to tasks, to be decision makers and makers of their own destiny. Therefore, education must see that it prepares not a few persons with a great knowledge but many persons with competent knowledge, capable of employing their faculties to the best possible use. If these are the expectations from Education then teacher education programmes or teacher preparation programmes will be called upon to shoulder even more serious responsibilities. There is thus the immediate need to address the TEP in light of the performance management viewpoint and indeed it begins its curriculum life skills - essential to all teachers who are ultimately responsible for their students development - be it physical mental, emotional or social.

Dove (1980) identified four principles while selecting objectives and content of TEP - one of the principles being the roles or expected of teachers. With the passage of time, scientific and technological, advancements, developments and challengers of the future, they are an addition to the expectations from teachers. There is thus the need for the TEP to reflect these roles clearly and avoid role ambiguity, role conflict and role overload as these result in depersonalization reduce accomplishment, lowered the job satisfaction and reduced occupational commitment.

Besides the 3Rs teachers are required to master the – 4th R - human relations - this being the principle reason for the existence of schools. Asley Motague rightly emphasised - all the knowledge in the world is worse than useless if it is not humanly understood and

humanly used. An intelligence that is not humane is the worst thing in the world.

A study conducted (2003) clearly indicate the weak areas (below 26%) of student teachers in (i) scientific attitude, (ii) discipline, (iii) patience and (iv) optimism related to the affective domain.. TEP is found to focus on cognitive development neglecting the affective.

Integration of life skills in TEP

It is assumed that life skills automatically develop in individuals with experience and maturity and therefore, the need to provide training for them has not been identified. The failure of students to survive in a competitive world has been attributed to various other factors and therefore life skills Education has been totally neglected.

Though TEP's have been modified several times they have failed to keep pace with the ever growing demands of a dynamic society. The teachers tasks are becoming more and more complex plus challenging - in an attempt to balance between the disseminating generating knowledge, inculcating values constitutional ideologies and the Indian ethos teachers find themselves totally handicapped. Thus TEP's focus and pedagogical theory and practicals are insufficient. It needs to prepare teachers with character, integrity, good values plus a positive attitude thereby equipping the them to become more responsive towards their social obligations

Covey S.R. (1998) and Khera S. (1998) have identified seven areas which constitute essential principles for effectiveness which are in harmony with natural laws of growth. They provide an incremental, sequential and highly immigrated approach to the development of personal and interpersonal effectiveness.

For teaching effectiveness it is necessary to internalize these principles and breakaway from certain deeply embedded habitual tendencies which violate these principles such as procrastination, impatience, criticalness, selfishness etc.

A study undertaken by Yeole C. & Sapre N.(2003) to measure 27 M.Ed. students the future teacher educators acquisition of life skills had alarming results. The seven areas considered were personal vision, personal leadership, personnel management, interpersonal leadership, empathic communication, creative Cooperation and balanced self renewal. Student's acquisition in two areas personal management (59%) and creative co operation 51% was just above average in the remaining five areas it ranged between 44% to 25%

The M.Ed. students who are at the apex level in the hierarchy of the teacher

education system in the age group 21-23 years are looked upon by the family and society as a responsible cards processing of the ability to help develop young school children into responsive citizens of the future. In view of these expectations are the findings of the above study indicated that these MEd. trainers have been unsuccessful in developing healthy life skills even after completing their entire education. The study clearly indicates the failure or neglect of education in developing life skills essential for preparing teachers with character, integrity, good values and a positive attitude - responsible torch bearers of a learning society.

It is essential to integrate the development of personal plus interpersonal life skills in the TEP's practical components.

Integrating life skills in the TEP's through performance management is essential.

Management of Education

Management is concerned with both objective and subjective phenomena. Management involves values, attitudes, techniques and behavioral patterns at both strategic and tactical levels.

Management is effective utilization of human and material resource to achieve enterprise objectives (William T. Gulule 1977).

Education and management are large and complex concepts. Education is the learning process by which values, attitudes, information and skills are acquired and integrated. Management of Education is the process of teaching and learning values attitudes; information and skills are acquired and integrated.

Performance management

TEP is a process of human resource management, where in resource, personnel, procedures and their strategies are managed with the aim of producing a efficient and the effective teachers, performance management is a means of addressing the requirement of the TEP it should provide the framework for internally auditing the means by which performance are evaluated at every step so that there is sufficient scope for this condition improvement.

The teacher has to perform various roles as leader, counsellor, guide, researchers, in very Limited time. Thus a performance management is a process which TEP's can adopt to assist them in their endeavor to contribute to a wider societal objectives by establishing a frame work in which the performance by the individuals can be directed monitored, motivated and refined entailing auditing of links.

The performance and management system is based on the contribution from the two theories of performance management namely - goal setting theory and expectancy theory.

Goal setting theory (Edwin Lock) 1968 states that if goals are specific, demanding but attainable with feedback of performance and are accepted by the employees. Then they help to motivate for superior performance and people are found to examine and modify their behaviour accordingly.

Expectancy theory (Victor Vroom 1964) the anticipated satisfaction of the valued goals causes individuals to adjust their behaviour accordingly.

Fig. 1- A Simple Expectancy Model (Mabey c and Salaman G).

With a combination of the theories the performance Management System for Teacher Education can be framed as follows:

Fig. 2 – Performance Management System for Teacher Education

To meet the changes, challenges, expectations and competencies of a 'knowledge society' full-fledged teacher resource development is aimed at, through the performance managed system of teacher education.

Wider strategic goals of the institution (government, aided, non-aided) are to be translated into goals for smaller groups and individuals - these will vary slightly as per the type of institution, whereas the syllabi, examination, duties allotted, work load etc. remains the same region wise.

Performance goals today remain focused on student - teachers examination results and not on teacher performance, leave alone student teachers contribution to the society as teachers. Process links between Efforts and Measured performance or performance and rewards remain unidentified and totally neglected.

If TEP is to be viewed as a professional preparation then well designed auditable procedures need to be developed to replace the prevailing system of assessing performance. For each of the practicum components, of the TEP i.e. practices teaching, micro teaching, SUPW etc. a performance management system for helping student teachers to reach the mastery level could comprise of the following procedure:

- i. identification of stages involved for a successful completion of the particular practical.
- ii. Corresponding expected behaviour, stage – wise.
- iii. Corresponding weightage / numerical indicator / marks stage wise.
- iv Specific individuals involved in the marking, stage-wise i.e. teacher-educator, peer, school teacher etc.
- v Entrusting specific responsibilities.
- vi Making the whole procedure known to all the concerned i.e. teacher-educators, student-teachers, school-teachers etc.
- vii Plan and procedure to provide formative and summative feedback and evaluation.
- viii Suggest measures for further improvement.

The procedure would provide specific guidelines for teacher-educators and student-teachers to undertake and complete each TEP practicum to the mastery level being assured that each stage is carefully evaluated and quality improved. Participative involvement of peers at each stage would help to strengthen the process links and through team spirit and a well audited performance deficiency (PD) can be identified, overcome and their causes studied.

To be regarded as professionals, teachers-educators and student-teachers have to be highly competent, committed to personal growth and sustained hard-work a self analysis helps to identify strengths, weaknesses, interests and aptitude. Once areas are identified and prioritized appropriate learning experiences can be pursued so as to result in more competent performance.

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